

THE IMPORTANCE OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE

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Abstract. *This article highlights the importance of teaching students in higher education using modern pedagogical technologies. Ways to improve the quality of education based on modern approaches are described.*

Keywords: *modernization, pedagogical technologies, quality of education, professional knowledge, etc.*

The principles of the socio-economic development of our republic in the modern period require further building up of our spiritual potential and economic power, their reorganization in such a way that it meets the requirements of the scientific and technological development of the 21st century, to a worthy place among the developed countries of the world. To do this, it is necessary to change the worldview of our people, especially our youth, to raise their knowledge and spirituality to the level of world standards. In solving such a complex social problem, domestic pedagogy, built on a scientific basis, bears great responsibility.

At present, when the process of reforms, modernization, modernization and improvement of science is taking place in our country, one of the most important priority areas is the further improvement of the spirituality of society, the achievement of the quality and effectiveness of education. the cultural upbringing of a person living in this society, the formation of an educated person as a cultural personality in socio-economic, mental and spiritual development, which manifests itself in various spheres of human activity, also depends on state policy.

The term modernization is defined in the sources as follows. For example, the Uzbek National Encyclopedia says: "Modernization (French moderne - een new, modern) - updating something, giving it a modern touch, changing it in accordance with modern requirements" [2.43].

“And in the process of education, modernization – this is the process of choosing the content of education based on the requirements of the era, introducing innovations into it, processing it, filling identified gaps, ensuring coherence and continuity” [3.211] – says researcher R.F.Safarova.

The first formation of educational technologies, its initial elements go back to very ancient times. Because the education of the young generation has been developing and improving in all times of mankind. As a result, pedagogical technologies started from the time when people began to engage in educational activities. Individual and group education methods appeared. With the emergence of schools, the methods of education also developed. Their improvement, as a result of

modernization in a new modern language, each subject began to be taught in certain methods and ways.

Today, that is, by the 21st century, the most advanced technologies have entered the world, including in the conditions of Uzbekistan, technologies that ensure the quality and effectiveness of historically formed education in modern methods of education, and facilitate the results obtained.

In the address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the 2023 Supreme Assembly, **2023 is the "Year of attention to people and quality education" in our country**, to be named as and found confirmation in the following opinions. We have set the priority task of ensuring the interests of people and their interests in the center of the state policy in Uzbekistan. It is clear to all of us that this policy will not be limited to one year, it will continue forever.

In fact, our most priceless wealth is our creative people, our prayerful parents, our humble generation, isn't it? We are trying to create all the necessary conditions for every person living in this country to live a peaceful and happy life, to be in good health, to get a good education, and to raise a family. we won't stop.

Improving the quality of education is the only correct way to the development of New Uzbekistan.

As our grandfather Yusuf Khos Hajib said:

"Where there is intelligence, there is greatness,
Where there is knowledge, there is greatness."

Therefore, we should continue the reforms we have started in this field, go to educational institutions, communicate more with teachers and trainers, and jointly solve the issues raised by them to improve the quality of educational work.

Modernization of the educational process is being carried out sufficiently in our country today. A regulation on the procedure for introducing the credit-module system into the educational process in higher education institutions has been developed, and starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, the educational process will gradually be introduced into the credit-module system in the higher educational institutions of the republic. The transfer procedure was introduced.

The quality of education is an important indicator of the successful operation of an educational institution, it is a system generator of internal management tasks of an educational institution.

The quality of education is an important aspect and set of characteristics of educational results that are able to satisfy the requirements of the learners themselves, the society, and the educational customers.

The results of the required level of educational quality can be achieved through a certain social pedagogical system. This system consists of the following systems: DTS; Normative model of future specialists; We can present the criteria and indicators for evaluating the quality of education and monitoring through the table below.

In the course of the lesson, the teacher not only imparts knowledge on the science program he is teaching, but also gives new scientific knowledge, while managing the educational process based on the plan, he checks and controls the level of knowledge acquisition of the students in the course of the lesson, and forms the knowledge and skills during study, the ability to think, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice.

Nowadays, the evaluation of knowledge (professional knowledge) and skills of pupils and students is one of the necessary parts of the educational process, and it is inextricably linked with how well the educational process is organized. Because by evaluating the knowledge and skills of the students, the progress achieved in preparing them as a student (student as a future specialist) at each stage of the educational process, as well as the shortcomings, monitoring the effectiveness of the team of pedagogues gives the opportunity to carry.

It is known that in professional practice, in the process of monitoring the formation of students' knowledge and skills, the following single pedagogical goals are set, which are necessary for them to become junior specialists, universally accepted and understandable to all of us:

- Provide solid knowledge of the basics of science;
- Formation of cognitive activity and logical thinking of students;
- Formation of interest in knowledge and profession in them;
- Formation of professional skills;
- Increase student's activity;
- The student should do it himself, work hard, find it himself;
- Creating an opportunity to learn from each other;
- Eliminate mental discomfort;
- Eliminate shyness;
- Create an opportunity for them to express their opinions;
- That the student is not afraid to make a mistake (has the right to make a mistake and correct it);
- Searching for a solution, teaching them to find a solution themselves;
- Creating conditions for free thinking;
- Communicate cooperatively with each other;
- Do not control the child during the lesson;
- Do not force or intimidate the student, do not squeeze;
- Efficient use of time;
- To be able to listen to the opinion, not to disagree, to observe the culture of asking questions;
- Respect for others' opinions and mutual respect;
- Teaching children to express their thoughts briefly and fluently;
- Kindness, sympathy, timely help to children;
- Prevention of mental discomfort that occurs when the student is answering in the group, etc.

However, in many cases, the question of what tasks, tasks and exercises students should be able to perform in order to demonstrate the achievement of these goals in practice remains unclear.

According to experienced teachers, the use of new technologies for assessing students' professional knowledge and skills, the use of new modifications of tests, the use of computer equipment and control training programs ensures the effective implementation of pedagogical monitoring of the educational process.

In the evaluation process, in order to ensure that students actively approach the educational process, it is possible to set criteria through the meaning and content of the information they are learning as knowledge and skills. Spiritualist B.G.Ananev states that in practice, two types of criteria for evaluating students' knowledge are used: quantitative and qualitative criteria, and conditionally explains them as follows:

1. Quantitative criteria are used on the basis of interval scales that help to analyze and draw conclusions using statistical methods. The consistency coefficient of the mastered educational material can be taken as these criteria.

2. Quality criteria cannot be directly measured on an interval scale, but are used in the analysis of the content of pedagogical events with the help of this scale. He explains that the quality criteria are applied based on the student's level of knowledge of the educational material, the level of understanding of the educational material, the level of acquisition of the educational material and intellectual skills [4].

The analysis of the content of the current labor education shows the need to modernize it based on the requirements of market relations. Modernization of labor education based on the requirements of market relations is very important nowadays. Therefore, by modernizing the results of the quality of education, a practical solution to these problems can be solved.

The process of "Modernization" in all aspects of society also applies to the process of education. Reforming the evaluation of students' knowledge in accordance with the requirements of the current era is the demand of the time.

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